

**POSSIBILITIES OF IMPROVING THE ACCURACY
OF MEASUREMENT HYDROSTATIC PRESSURE MEASUREMENT
WITH STRAIN GAUGE SENSORS**

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To increase the accuracy the multichannel principle is used for constructing the invariant systems. The method of pressure measurement with the use of several strain gauges of different sensitivity approximated by polynomials of degree m for pressure and system n for temperature, forming a system of $(m+1)(n+1)-1$ linear algebraic equations from the transformation functions as products of polynomials and the relative changes in resistances tenzoristor and the system solution relative to the measured pressure Variants of devices for interrogating strain gauges at direct and alternating currents are considered.

Keywords: *pressure, tenzoristor, conversion function.*

Introduction. Tenzoristor of hydrostatic pressure are widely used in various fields of the national economy, and in oceanology in particular [Levashov, 2003; Stepanyuk, 1986]. These gauges operate in the marine environment at different temperatures, are relatively cheap, and provide accuracy of the order of a few tenths of a percent. However, such accuracy is not sufficient for solving many problems and, in particular, for measuring the local density of water at high external pressures.

Main part. Sensors in known measuring devices contain four tenzoristor (formerly metal, now semiconductor), placed on pressure-sensitive membranes and converting the mechanical displacement into electrical resistance. Tenzoristor are usually included in the shoulders of a four-arm bridge with different signs of sensitivity in adjacent shoulders to obtain a larger amplitude of the output signal on the diagonal of the bridge. Analysis shows that such a scheme doubles the nonlinearity of the through channel relative to the pressure, which initially takes place with inaccurate manufacture of tenzoristor and their resistance dependence on the temperature. The use of the bridge scheme of tenzoristor in replacement of metal tenzoristor for semiconductor ones, sensitivity of which is two orders of magnitude higher, has lost its meaning and significantly limited the possibilities of combating nonlinearity and temperature dependence.

If the principles of the theory of invariance are used to improve the instrumental accuracy, the hydrostatic pressure meters should be performed integrally [Vaganov, 1983] with k separate tenzoristors transducers, which have significant differences in sensitivity β_{ij} to pressure P and in sensitivity α_{is} to temperature θ . The gauge model will be in the form of SLAU

$$R_{i0} \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_{ij} P^j \right) \left(1 + \sum_{s=1}^n \alpha_{is} \theta^s \right) = R_i, \quad i = \overline{1, k}, \quad k = (m+1)(n+1) - 1$$

and pressure P is calculated from the solution of this system at the coefficients β_{ij}, α_{is} , $j = \overline{1, m}$, $s = \overline{1, n}$, R_{i0} and measured R_i , without measuring temperature θ . It is assumed [Gaysky V.A., 2022] that with increasing the degree m and n of the approximation polynomials in the strain gauge model the accuracy of the meter will increase.

For example, presumably with $m = 4, n = 4, k = 24$ get 0.01%.

The structural diagram of the proposed device for polling strain gauges with direct current is shown in Fig. 1.

The device includes a block 1 tenzoristors $1_1, \dots, 1_k$ placed on the perception of the pressure membrane and connected to the voltage out block 2, block 3 current keys $3_1, \dots, 3_k$, serving to supply on tenzoristors with direct current from the output block 4 current generator, made on a transis 5 with current-forming model resistor 6 denomination R_0 in the emitter and differential amplifier 7, whose first input is connected to the voltage source output chain voltage divider connected to the resistors 8 and 9, denomination r_1 and r_2 , the second input amplifier connected to the emitter of the transistor, and the output is fed to the base of the transistor 5. To remove the voltage from the tenzoresistors is a block 10 of potential switches $10_1, \dots, 10_k$, the output of which is fed to the block 11 generating the output signal at the first input of the differential amplifier 12, in which the second input is connected with the output of a voltage source 2, and the output is fed to the input of an analog-digital converter 13. The block 14 is used to control the operation of current and potential switches.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the device for interrogation tenzoristors with direct current

Conclusion. Thus, the proposed method of measuring fluid pressure and the device for its implementation improve the accuracy by reducing the error of nonlinearity of tenzoristors and the influence of temperature, and simplify the implementation due to the possibility of imprecise manufacturing.

List of references:

Levashov D.E. Sensors and gauges of hydrostatic pressure // Technique of expeditionary research: Instrumental methods and technical means of evaluation of field-significant environmental factors. Moscow: Izd vo VNIRO, 2003. C. 51-67.

Stepanyuk I.A. Oceanological measuring transducers. L.: Hydrometeoizdat, 1986. 272 c.

Vaganov V.I. Integral thermal conversion. Moscow: Energoatomizdat, 1983. 136 c.

Gaysky V.A. Method and devices with strain gauges for measuring hydrostatic pressure. Environmental Control Systems. 2022. 2(48). C. 36-45.